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„Üzleti szoftverek fejlesztését támogató kódgenerálás alapú
keretrendszer fejlesztése és piaci bevezetése”

User Guide

RTS

product engineering

NEMZETI KUTATÁSI, FEJLESZTÉSI
ÉS INNOVÁCIÓS HIVATAL

AZ INNOVÁCIÓ LENDÜLETE

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1. Introduction to Mike

What is Mike?

Mike is a declarative language which allows you to define data models and user interface structures in a concise and straightforward manner. Based on the description written in the Mike format, Mike will generate the Java code for a full application which can be run and deployed immediately. The generated Java code itself can also be freely modified and extended to better suit your needs. The Mike descriptor and the generated Java code can be developed in parallel, and Mike will not overwrite your changes. Instead, they will be merged in a similar manner to a version control system such as `git`. In this way, Mike is your cooperative virtual colleague.

The following sections will walk you through the process of writing a Mike descriptor for a hypothetical example use case and provide an overview of the features available in the Mike language. (For questions about specific details and edge cases, consult the Developer guide.)

An introductory example

Let's begin by creating a basic Customer Relationship Management (CRM) system with just a single entity, `Customer`, and a single page displaying a table of all customers recorded by the system.

```
# This is the data model
data {
  entity Customer {
    email: String @primary
    name: String
    phoneNumber: String
  }
}

# And this is the user interface
ui {
  page CustomersPage @home {
    table CustomersTable: Customer
  }
}
```

Generating and running the application

Follow these steps:

1. Sign up for a developer account at codemike.dev.
2. On the dashboard, create a new project called “CRM”, and copy the API key that was generated for it.

3. Download the newest version of the Mike CLI tools from the Releases page and follow the installation instructions listed there.
4. Create a new directory to hold the application, such as `crm`.
5. Enter this directory, and issue the `mike init` command.
6. The `init` command will ask a series of questions. For the project's name, use "CRM". When it asks for your API key, use the key copied in step 2. For the remainder, you can accept the default values. This will result in the creation of two configuration files, `config.yaml` and `mike.yaml`, and a dummy Mike descriptor file, `main.mike`.
7. Copy and paste the example code from above into the `crm/mike/main.mike` file, overwriting its previous contents.
8. Issue the `mike generate` command. This will create the Java code and other required files for the application.
9. To run the application, there are two main alternatives. If *Docker* is available, the simplest is to invoke `docker compose up`, which will start the application with no other dependencies required. (This may take several minutes.)
10. If you prefer to run the application *without Docker*, first make sure you have *Java* and *Maven* installed and a *PostgreSQL* server running, and edit the generated `src/main/resources/application.properties` file to provide the correct address, port, and credentials for connecting to the *PostgreSQL* server. Issue the `mvn package` command, which will compile the source code for the generated application (this may take several minutes), and run the application with `java -jar target/crm-1.0-SNAPSHOT.jar`. (Alternatively, you may of course open the generated Java project in your IDE of choice, and compile and run it from there.)
11. Navigate to <http://localhost:8888> in your web browser to see the running application.
12. We are initially greeted by the login page. To log in as the administrator, the username and password are both "admin" by default. (These can be changed from within the application.)

If all goes well, you will see an initially-empty table with an "Add new" button you can use to add new customers to the system.

Explaining the example

Every Mike descriptor contains two main top-level sections, `data { ... }` which specifies the data model (database schema), and `ui { ... }` which specifies the structure of the user interface.

In this example, the data model consists of just a single `Customer` entity with three members, each with type `String` (holding textual data). The `email` member is marked `@primary`, which means it will be used as the entity's primary key in the database. Every entity must have exactly one member designated as the `@primary` one.

The user interface, meanwhile, so far consists of a single page called `CustomersPage`. This page is marked as the `@home` page, which means it will be the page that's initially displayed after user login. (If no pages are marked as `@home`, an empty page will be created to serve as the home page by default.) This page contains a single `table` declaration named `CustomersTable`, which specifies `Customer` as the entity type to be displayed in the table. By default, the table will contain a column for each member of the `entity`, and supports creating, viewing, editing, and deleting instances. (Later chapters will describe how to make different choices for the table's contents and behavior, if so desired.)

In terms of its structure, a Mike descriptor consists of a nested hierarchy of *declarations*, which are the lines that begin with a keyword (here `data`, `ui`, `entity`, `page`, and `table`) or a name (here `email`, `name`, and `phoneNumber`). A declaration may be annotated with one or more *attributes* that modify its behavior, such as `@primary` and `@home`, and may have one or more *child declarations* specified within braces, `{ ... }`. The declarations, attributes, and other features supported by Mike will be introduced in the rest of this Guide. (You may also consult the Developer guide for full details.)

Each declaration – other than the top-level `data` and `ui` blocks – has a *name* (in this example, `Customer`, `email`, `CustomersPage`, and so on). These names serve a dual purpose: they may be used to refer to that declaration from within the descriptor itself (for example, `table CustomersTable: Customer` refers to the previously declared `entity Customer`), *and* they will be used for the names of `classes` and other elements in the generated code, so for example, a Java-side `class Customer` will be generated based on this descriptor. (Note that naming conventions on the Mike side are *enforced*, so for example, we could *not* have written `entity customer` or `Name: String!`)

Keywords and names are sometimes optional. In the above example, `name: String` is short for member `name: String`, because `member` is the *default keyword* within the context of an `entity`. Similarly, the `entity` keyword itself may be omitted from `Customer`, if desired. And if we were to simply write `table: Customer` without specifying a name, a default name for it would be derived from its type, which in this case would be equivalent to writing `table CustomersTable: Customer` (note the singular “Customer”, as opposed to “Customers” in our manually-written example). Full details about which keywords are optional and how default names are derived are available in the Developer guide.

Comments, which will be ignored by Mike, may be written beginning with the `#` character, and continue until the end of the line.

What's next?

In this simple example, we've only scratched the surface of Mike's features. In the following chapters, we'll expand our CRM system to include more entities and relationships and more sophisticated UI structures. We'll learn about topics such as:

- Defining relationships between entities (e.g., connecting Sales to Customers)
- Creating multiple pages and linking them together
- Using details views and data entry forms
- Customizing the UI with different labels and layouts

By the end of this Guide, you'll have a detailed understanding of how to use Mike to create an application that satisfies your individual needs and requirements.

2. Entities and relationships

In this chapter, we'll build upon our basic CRM system by adding more entities, creating multiple pages, and defining relationships between entities.

Multiple entities, pages, and the navigation element

Let's start by expanding our data model in the `main.mike` file to include Sales and Products, in addition to our existing Customer entity. We will also add a separate page in the UI for each of these.

```
data {
  entity Customer {
    email: String @primary
    name: String
    phoneNumber: String
  }

  entity Product {
    sku: String @primary
    name: String
    price: Float
  }

  entity Sale {
    id: Int @primary
    date: Date
    totalAmount: Float
  }
}

ui {
  navigation {
    item CustomersItem: CustomersPage
    item ProductsItem: ProductsPage
    item SalesItem: SalesPage
  }

  page CustomersPage @home {
    table CustomersTable: Customer
  }
}
```

```
}  
  
page ProductsPage {  
    table ProductsTable: Product  
}  
  
page SalesPage {  
    table SalesTable: Sale  
}  
}
```

What's new here?

- The `Int`, `Float`, and `Date` built-in types can be used to store integers (42), floating-point a.k.a. decimal numbers (3.14), and dates ("2012-12-21"), respectively.
- When `Int` is used together with `@primary`, as in the `Sale` entity, the integer ID will always be auto-incremented by the system, rather than provided by the end user. (And the same applies to the `UUID` type, which we have not used so far, but which would always be generated randomly when used with `@primary`.)
- The `navigation` element results in a navigation drawer being displayed on the left-hand side of each page, which can be used to navigate to the other top-level pages of the application.
- The navigation drawer will contain a menu item for each declared `item`. The name of the page it links to is specified after the colon (:). The name of the `item` itself (before the colon) is optional. And, although not demonstrated here, we can also use nested `items` to create submenus. (At most one additional level of nesting is currently supported.)

We can now navigate to separate tables for each of our three entity types but, so far, they are completely independent of each other. The next section will demonstrate how to create relationships between them.

To generate and run this application, follow the steps from the earlier section, starting from step 7 if you've already generated an application from the previous example. (If you haven't, then of course, start from the first step. The only difference is which example code to copy into the `main.mike` file.)

Relationships between entities

Let's now flesh out our data model by adding relationships between the entities:

```
data {  
    entity Customer {  
        email: String @primary  
        name: String!  
        phoneNumber: String  
        sales: [Sale] @mappedBy(customer) # (new)  
    }  
}
```

```

}

entity Product {
  sku: String @primary
  name: String!
  price: Float!
}

entity Sale {
  id: Int @primary
  customer: Customer! # (new)
  products: [Product] # (new)
  date: Date
  totalAmount: Float
}
}

```

(The `ui` section is the same as before.)

There are several new concepts here. We will consider them one at a time.

The `Type!` syntax means that the given member is *mandatory*: at the database level, it is `NOT NULL`, and in the UI, a value for it *must* be provided by the end user when creating and editing the entity’s instances. This syntax is actually shorthand for an attribute called `@mandatory`: if we write `name: String @mandatory`, this means exactly the same thing as `name: String!`. By default, anything not marked mandatory is considered optional (nullable); except that `@primary` also *implies* `@mandatory`, i.e., the primary key must always be assigned a value.

We will return to the `[Type]` syntax and `@mappedBy` in a moment.

As we can see, each `entity` type we declare can subsequently be used in the types of entity members, such as `customer: Customer!` within `Sale`. (Declarations can be in any order, and do *not* need to precede their uses, as we can see with the `sales` member in `Customer`.) If we think of this in programming language terms, it’s fairly straightforward: an object of one type holds a reference to an object of another type. In database terms, meanwhile, we’re defining a *relation* between the two types (or more concretely, between the database tables storing their respective instances). In the case of `customer: Customer!` in `Sale`, it means that each `Sale` is associated with exactly one `Customer`. (In the reverse direction, however, a given `Customer` can implicitly be associated with any number of `Sales`!)

This brings us to `[Type]` and `@mappedBy`. In a similar way to how `Type!` means “mandatory value”, `[Type]` means “many values” – and is shorthand for the `@many` attribute. So in the line `sales: [Sale] @mappedBy(customer)` within the `Customer` entity, we’ve now explicitly specified, in the form of Mike syntax, what was mentioned at the end of the previous paragraph: that each `Customer` can be associated with multiple `Sales`.

The `@mappedBy(customer)` attribute, meanwhile, ties the two together: it says that the `Sales` a given `Customer` is associated with are *the same* as the `Sales` which refer to that `Customer` (through their `customer` member). They’re two sides of the same coin. This is important, because it’s not the only possible state of affairs! If we were to leave off the `@mappedBy` attribute, then the `customer` and `sales` members would be, metaphorically speaking, each the “heads” side of two *separate* coins. This is perhaps easier to understand with an example:

With `@mappedBy`:

Sale.id Sale.customer

1 bob@company.com
2 jane@corp.net
3 jane@corp.net

Customer.email Customer.sales

bob@company.com 1
jane@corp.net 2, 3

Here, the contents of `Customer.sales` is *always* the inverse of `Sale.customer`. In the UI, only the contents `Sale.customer` can be provided by the end user, and `Customer.sales` will automatically reflect those changes wherever it is displayed.

Without `@mappedBy`:

Sale.id Sale.customer

1 bob@company.com
2 jane@corp.net
3 jane@corp.net

Customer.email Customer.sales

bob@company.com 1, 2, 3
jane@corp.net 3

In this case, the contents of `Customer.sales` can be anything – it doesn’t need to be related to `Sale.customer` in any way. (It *could* happen to hold the same values as in the previous table, but it would be a mere coincidence.) In the UI, the contents of `Sale.customer` and `Customer.sales` can both be edited independently by the end user, and neither has any influence on the other.

Now if, in fact, we were to simply delete `@mappedBy(customer)` from the above, Mike would issue a warning, asking us to clarify our intent: did we *really* mean to define two completely independent relations, rather than the forwards and reverse directions of the same relation? This is to guard against `@mappedBy` being omitted purely by accident. If it was truly deliberate, then

we can use another attribute – `@unidirectional` – to make our intention clear. (In the context of the above example, it would suffice to add `@unidirectional` to *either* the `customer` *or* the `sales member`, and then Mike won’t feel the need to warn us any more.)

It’s worth noting that declaring a corresponding “backwards reference” member with `@mappedBy` (like `sales` in the example) for each “forwards reference” member (like `customer`) is *entirely optional*. We can delete the `sales` line, and there would be no adverse consequences. Conversely, within `Product`, we could add the line `sales: [Sale] @mappedBy(products)`, which we had heretofore skipped.

A `@mappedBy` member can be considered “virtual” in the sense that it is not stored or represented in any way in the underlying database: it is solely a higher-level convenience. The practical effect of adding a `@mappedBy` member is twofold:

- In details views (accessed by clicking the “view” action, depicted as an eye icon on a row of a `table`), there will be an additional field showing the contents of the `@mappedBy` member.
- We can refer to this member explicitly from elsewhere in the Mike descriptor: for example, when choosing which columns should be displayed within a `table`. (How that is done will be the subject of the next chapter.)

Finally, let us return to the `products: [Product]` line within the `Sale` entity. As there’s no `@mappedBy` here (nor could there be, since no member of `Product` refers to `Sale`), the contents of this member are directly stored in the database, in the same way as described for `Customer.sales` in the “without `@mappedBy`” scenario from above.

However, whereas a scalar (non-`@many`) reference to an `entity` is represented in the database as a column holding that entity’s primary key type together with a foreign key constraint, a `@many` member (recall that `products: [Product]` is shorthand for `products: Product @many`) is stored as a separate *relation table*. The relation table has two columns, one which holds a foreign key to the database table representing the referring `entity` (`Sale` in the example), and the other, to the referred-to `entity` (`Product`). If we recall that each `Sale` is associated with any number of `Products` and each `Product` with any number of `Sales` (which we can make explicit by adding a `@mappedBy` member in `Product`, as mentioned earlier), then the aforementioned relation table records which *pairs* of `Sale` and `Product` are associated with *each other*. Since many-to-many relationships are symmetric, if we want to explicitly declare both sides of the relation, then which of the two sides to put the `@mappedBy` attribute on is usually a matter of taste.

At the level of a programming language, the `products` member holds a *collection* of `Product` instances, such as a `Set<Product>`.

To recap:

- A member such as `customer: Customer` defines a many-to-one relationship.
- The corresponding one-to-many relationship can be declared explicitly, if desired, with a member like `sales: [Sale] @mappedBy(customer)` in the referred-to entity.
- A member like `products: [Product]` defines a many-to-many relationship, and the inverse direction of the relationship can be explicitly declared in the same way as in the previous point.
- (One-to-one relationships can also be created using the `@unique` attribute, which will be discussed in a later chapter.)

Finally, what has changed in the generated UI compared to the one generated from the example descriptor in the previous section?

- The table for `Sale` now contains a column for the associated `Customer`, and when creating a new `Sale`, a `Customer` must also be selected from among the previously created instances.
- When creating or editing a `Sale`, any number of previously-created `Product` instances may also be associated with it, and these are also displayed when viewing the details for a given `Sale`.
- When viewing the details for a `Customer`, we now also see a list of the `Sales` made to that customer. For now, this happens in a somewhat suboptimal fashion: each `Sale` is displayed in the form of its automatically generated numeric `id`. (In general, every entity is displayed by default as the contents of its `@primary` member). In a later chapter, we will see how to override this default and choose a better display format using the `@display` attribute.

1. Nothing forbids having, e.g., `customer1: Customer` and `customer2: Customer` both within the same entity, so `@mappedBy` requires specifying which member is involved *explicitly*.

3. Refining the user interface

Up to this point, the pages used for creating, viewing, and editing entities have been generated entirely automatically, and the columns displayed in a `table` have always corresponded to the entity's members. In this chapter, we will learn how to customize the UI in more flexible ways to fit our requirements more closely.

Customizing table columns

So far, whenever we wrote a `table` component, Mike has automatically expanded it to a definition like this one:

```
table SalesTable: Sale {
  column: id
  column: customer
  column: date
  column: totalAmount
}
```

By default, a `column` is included for each member of the `entity` except for those which have a `@many` attribute (due to performance considerations), while default columns for `@primary` keys of type `UUID` are set to hidden by default (as these are generated randomly, and are not meaningful for end users). (A default column that refers to an `entity` will also link to its view page by default; how to achieve this manually will be described a bit later.)

If we prefer, we can also choose to display different columns manually:

```
table SalesTable: Sale {
  column: customer.name
  column: customer.email
  column: date
  column: totalAmount
  column: products.name
}
```

This will add separate columns for the customer's name and e-mail address, and will add a new column with a comma-separated list of the names of the products that were sold. When we use a dot, such as in `customer.email`, this is known as a *member path*: `Sale` has a member called `customer`, and `Customer` has a member called `email`, so we can access this sub-member and display it directly.

When a member is `@many`, as with `products`, its contents are displayed in the column as a comma-separated list, and the same is true if we access a nested member (here `.name`) *within* that `@many` member, in which case the contents of *that* member specifically are presented in the list. (Note that, however, displaying the contents of a `@many` member within *another* `@many` member is not currently supported: at most one `@many` member may be used in each path.)

Customizing the create page

Whenever we've used a `table`, Mike has also automatically created associated pages for creating, editing, and viewing instances of that `entity` type. These can also be explicitly declared using Mike syntax, and the default create page for `Sale` looks like this:

```
page SaleCreatePage {
  form SaleCreateForm: Sale
}
```

Much like how the `table` component is used to display existing instances, the `form` component is used to create new ones.

We can specify a custom create page like so:

```
page SalesPage {
  table SalesTable: Sale @createPage(NewSalePage)
}

page NewSalePage {
  form NewSaleForm: Sale {
    input: customer
    input: products
  }
}
```

Here, all we have changed is that for demonstration purposes, we have removed the input fields for `date` and `totalAmount`. We will learn about further customization possibilities in a following chapter.

By default, if no `inputs` are specified explicitly, then a `form` will contain an input field for each member of the `entity`, except for those with a `@mappedBy` or a `@value` attribute (which will be introduced in a later chapter), and except for the `@primary` member if it's of type `Int` or `UUID` (because values for these are provided by the system, not the user). A create form *must* include an input for every `@mandatory` member, while for the others, whether to include it is up to us. (In contrast to `columns`, `inputs` do *not* support nested member paths, only top-level members within the given `entity`.)

If, for any reason, we want to disable creating new entities in a given `table` entirely, then instead of a `@createPage`, we can use `@omitted`:

```
table SalesTable: Sale @omitted(CREATE)
```

In this case, the code for creating new entity instances will be completely omitted from the code generated for the `table`.

Customizing the edit page

The default edit page Mike creates for us looks like this:

```
page SaleEditPage requires Sale as sale {
  form SaleEditForm: Sale using sale
}
```

Two new, and closely related, features can be observed here. Unlike the create page seen earlier, an edit page logically needs to operate on an *existing* entity instance. To declare that the page is capable of receiving such an `entity` instance, we write `requires Sale`, while `as sale` specifies that, *within* the page, we can refer to the received `Sale` instance using the name `sale`. These are analogous to the type and the name of a function parameter, respectively. When pressing the edit button in a table row (depicted as a pencil icon), it will pass *that* entity instance

to our `page` while navigating to it. (And since such a `page` *requires* a `Sale` object in order to function, this means it can't be used as a navigation item.)

Continuing on to the `form` declaration, meanwhile, `using` signifies that this form will be used to *edit* an entity instance: in this case, the `sale` instance received by the encompassing `page`. A `form` with a `using` clause is an *edit form*, while a `form` without one is a *create form*.

Declaring a custom edit page can now be done as we might expect:

```
page SalesPage {
  table SalesTable: Sale @editPage(ModifySalePage)
}

page ModifySalePage requires Sale as sale {
  form ModifySaleForm: Sale using sale {
    input: products
    input: date
    input: totalAmount
  }
}
```

The effect of this definition is that the `customer` of a `Sale` (which we have omitted from among the `inputs`!) may *not* be edited after the fact by using the edit button in the `SalesTable`'s generated UI, only its other members may be.

If we wish to disable the editing of items in a `table`, we can use `@omitted(EDIT)` in the same way as with `@omitted(CREATE)` above; and relatedly, we can also use `@omitted(DELETE)` to disable their deletion. To disable *all three* of these at once, we can use the `@readonly` attribute, which serves as a shorthand for the combination of the three `@omitted` attributes seen so far.

We can also use `@omitted(DELETE)` on a `form` so that the form can only be used to edit entity instances and not to delete them.

Customizing the view page

The final customizable action page is the view page. Its default definition looks like this:

```
page SaleDetailsPage requires Sale as sale {
  details SaleDetails: Sale using sale
}
```

The `details` element seen here is used for displaying a non-editable detailed view of a single entity instance. As seen earlier with the edit page and edit form, in order to view an entity instance, we need to equip the page with `requires Sale as sale` to be able to receive it, which we then pass on to the `details` element via the `using sale` clause. (For the record, a `details` element *without* a `using` clause is also technically permitted for prototyping purposes, but it has no contents to display and serves no useful function otherwise.)

By default, a `details` will have a `field` for every member of the displayed entity, except for the `@primary` key if it's of type `UUID`.

To customize it:

```
page SalesPage {
  table SalesTable: Sale @viewPage(ViewingSalePage)
}

page ViewingSalePage requires Sale as sale {
  details SaleDetails: Sale using sale @editPage(SaleEditPage) {
    field: id
    field: customer.name @link
    field: customer.email @link(ViewingCustomerPage)
    field: date
    field: totalAmount
  }
  table SaleProductsTable: Product using sale.products
}
```

This example demonstrates several new features:

- The `details` element also supports specifying a custom `@editPage` (not, however, a `@createPage` or `@viewPage`, which are not applicable for a `details`), and `@omitted(EDIT)`, `@omitted(DELETE)`, and `@readonly` can likewise be used.
- As with the `columns` of a `table`, the `fields` of a `details` also support displaying the contents of *member paths*, in essentially the same way.
- The `@link` attribute functions similarly to `@viewPage`, but for an individual `field` specifically: the field's contents are displayed as a clickable link, which will navigate to a view page for the entity instance referred to *by that field* (in the above example, the `customer`). This attribute can also be used on `inputs` and `columns` in the same way. If no argument for the attribute is specified, then it uses the same default view page as `tables` do; and if a custom page *is* specified, then it goes to that page. (In the above example, both modes can be seen, although only for the sake of demonstration: in this case there's no practical reason for the `email` field to use a different page than `name` does.)
- Although we haven't encountered it so far, a `page` can of course contain multiple elements! They are laid out vertically below each other by default.
- The `table` element also supports a `using` clause, in which case, instead of *all* existing instances of the given entity type, it will display *specifically* the instances referred to by a `@many` member of a given entity instance. Here, we are using this to view the `products` that were sold in a more detailed format, as opposed to including `field: products` in the `SaleDetails` itself (which would show them as merely a comma-separated list).
- While we have previously encountered *member paths*, the `sale.products` path used here is called a *reference path*: its first component is *not* the name of a member, but

the name of a `page` parameter (the one introduced with `requires Sale as sale`). After that first component, however, subsequent nested members can be accessed in the same way as with member paths!

(If we desired to, we could have chosen custom `columns` for this table as well, in the same way as before, but for now, we accept the default ones.)

And (as we might expect by this point), if we want to disable the ability to view item details in a table, then we can use `@omitted(VIEW)` for this purpose.

Other table customization features

The `table` and `column` elements support a number of other features and attributes we haven't covered so far.

The most significant of these is `@searchBar`. If specified on a `table`, its UI will be extended with a text field for searching among the textual contents of the data displayed by the table, and the table will then show only the rows with matching hits. (All of the data existing in the database is searched, not only the parts that are currently visible on the screen.) By default, the search happens in all table columns (including hidden ones!) of type `String`, plus columns of `entity` type, in which case those `String` members will be searched which contribute to the entity's textual representation in the table cells. (By default, this is just the `@primary` member, but this can be customized using the `@display` attribute, discussed in the next chapter.)

Alternatively, we can also explicitly specify one or more members or *member paths* as arguments to the `@searchBar` attribute, in which case the search will be performed in the contents of *those* paths. (The paths specified here do *not* necessarily need to correspond to any of the members or paths that were declared as `columns`!)

And if we've applied the `@searchBar` attribute, then we can optionally also use `@searchBarDefault("example text...")` to specify the default contents of the search field.

Along with the optional table-level search bar, the table also has *filters* on each column which can likewise be used to restrict the table's contents according to certain criteria, depending on the type of the column: for example, in the case of a `Date` column, the user can specify a date range. If we *don't* want these filters to be present, then we can use `@hiddenFilters` to hide them.

We can also set individual `columns` to be hidden *by default* using the `@hidden` attribute. The end user can however choose to make them visible again, if they so desire.

And finally, we can also specify a default sort order for the rows of the table by applying the `@sorted` attribute to one or more columns. If specified on only one `column`, the table will be sorted according to that column's contents by default. (As with `@hidden`, this is only a default,

and the end user will be free to sort by different columns instead.) We can use the optional `@sorted(ASC)` or `@sorted(DESC)` argument to specify whether the order should be ascending or descending (the default is ascending). If we want to sort by *multiple* columns at the same time, then we need to add a further argument to each `@sorted` attribute to specify their relative priority: `@sorted(ASC, 1)`, `@sorted(DESC, 2)`, and so on (*both* arguments must be provided in this case). Rows will initially be sorted according to the column with the highest priority (1) and, in the event of ties between one or more rows, they will be broken based on the contents of the next-highest priority column (2, 3, ...), and so on.

4. Customizing UI appearance

In this chapter, we'll learn how to arrange components into layouts, alter titles and textual display formats, and other fine-tuning to enhance user-friendliness and visual appeal.

Containers and layouts

As we've already seen, a page can contain multiple elements which are arranged vertically by default. We can choose a different arrangement using the `@layout` attribute:

```
page ViewingSalePage requires Sale as sale @layout(HORIZONTAL) {
  details SaleDetails: Sale using sale
  table SaleProductsTable: Product using sale.products
}
```

The other available options are:

- **VSPLIT:** The two components are divided by a vertical splitter bar, which can be dragged to adjust their relative sizes. (The page must have *exactly* two child elements in this case.)
- **TABBED:** This results in a tabbed view, with one tab for each child element. The titles of the tabs are taken from the elements' `@title` attributes, which is discussed further below.

To nest different layouts within each other, we can use a container:

```
page ViewingSalePage requires Sale as sale {
  details SaleDetails: Sale using sale
  container TablesContainer @layout(VSPLIT) {
    table SaleProductsTable: Product using sale.products
    table OtherSalesToCustomer: Sale using sale.customer.sales
  }
}
```

Both `containers` and `pages` support the same `@layout` options (a `page` can be thought of as having an implicit top-level `container`). Containers can be nested within each other to arbitrary depth.

Titles, headings, and icons

By default, the displayed titles of UI elements are determined based on their Mike-level names by splitting them into words at capitalization boundaries (for example, `SaleDetails` becomes “*Sale details*”). To choose different titles, we can use the `@title` attribute:

```
table CustomersTable: Customer {
  column: email @title("E-mail")
  ...
}
form NewCustomerForm: Customer {
  input: email @title("E-mail") @placeholder("jane.doe@example.com")
  ...
}
```

(This works the same way for `fields`, as well.)

Incidentally, as also demonstrated above, we can specify placeholder text for `input` fields, which will be shown until the user enters a value, by using the `@placeholder` attribute.

Since repeating the same title on *every* element where a given `entity` member is displayed may grow tiresome, we also have the option of specifying the title directly within the `entity` itself:

```
entity Customer {
  email: String @primary @title("E-mail")
  ...
}
```

In this case, `@title("E-mail")` will be used as the *default* title on all `columns`, `fields`, and `inputs` that display the contents of the `email` member; but we can still override it on a case-by-case basis with a `@title` attribute directly on the UI element, if needed.

In the case of nested member paths, such as `field: customer.email`, the default title is derived from the *last* path component, i.e., in this case it would be either “*E-mail*” or “*Email*”, depending on whether we’ve applied `@title("E-mail")` to the `email` member as shown above.

We can also use `@title` on `container`, `table`, `details`, and `form` elements, but this will *only* have an effect when they are contained within a `page` or `container` that has a `TABBED` layout, as described earlier.

We can also apply titles to `pages` and `navigation` items:

```
page CustomersPage @title("List of customers") { ... }

page ProductsPage @title("All products") { ... }

navigation {
  item: CustomersPage @title("Customers")
  item: ProductsPage @title("Products")
}
```

The specified `page` title will appear in the browser’s tab bar or title bar. If we omit the `@title` for an `item`, but do provide one for the `page` it references, then the `item`’s title will also be taken from the `page`’s title by default.

Navigation `items` can also have icons, specified using the `@icon` attribute:

```
item: ProductsPage @icon("fas:box-full")
```

Icon names are specified using the [FontAwesome format](#).

And finally, we can add additional heading elements to “block-level” UI components by using the `@heading` attribute:

```
table CustomersTable: Customer @heading("All Customers")
```

The `@heading` attribute is supported for `navigation`, `page`, `container`, `table`, `details`, and `form` declarations. If a heading is specified, then the element’s *title* will also use the same text by default. This is primarily relevant for `pages` and for elements within `TABBED` layouts.

When using `@heading` *on* or *within* a `page` that has a `requires ... as ...` clause, we also have the option of expanding it into a *template string* using *reference path* parameters:

```
page ViewingSalePage requires Sale as sale {
  details SaleDetails: Sale using sale @heading("Sale to {0} on {1}",
sale.customer.name, sale.date)
}
```

(Reference paths were also discussed earlier in the context of `using` clauses.)

This will display a heading of the form “*Sale to Bob Smith on 2021-03-16*”. Template strings are further described in the next section.

Display formats

Whereas titles and headings are displayed *alongside* data, we can customize the display format of the *data itself* using the `@prefix`, `@suffix`, and `@display` attributes:

```
table SalesTable: Sale {
```

```
column: customer @display("{0} ({1})", name, email)
column: totalAmount @suffix(" USD") # (for example)
}
```

The `@display` attribute can only be used with `entity` types, while `@prefix` and `@suffix` are only valid for non-`entity` types. All three attributes are available for `columns`, `fields`, as well as `inputs`.

As might be expected, `@prefix` and `@suffix` prepend or append (respectively) the given text to the displayed value. They can also be used together.

Meanwhile, `@display` substitutes its parameters into the provided *template string*: `{0}` is replaced by the first parameter, `{1}` by the second, and so on. The parameters are provided in the form of *member paths*, where the first path component is a member of the `entity` being displayed: in the above example, that is `Customer`, since that's the type of the `column` the `@display` attribute is used on. (And not `Sale`, which is the type for the entire *table*!).

As we have already seen with `@title`, since specifying `@display` separately on each `column`, `field`, and `input` can be repetitive, it can also be specified at the `entity` level:

```
entity Customer @display("{0} ({1})", name, email) {
    email: String @primary @title("E-mail")
    name: String!
    ...
}

entity Sale @display("Sale to {0} on {1}", customer.name, date) {
    id: Int @primary
    customer: Customer!
    date: Date
    ...
}
```

And likewise as with `@title`, the `entity-level` `@display` will then be used as the *default*, but can still be overridden on the individual `columns`, `fields`, and `inputs` if needed.

Language resource files

Every textual string displayed in the UI is added to the *language resource files*, typically located at `src/main/resources/messages.properties` in the generated project. These can be used to localize (translate) the application into different languages. For more details on that process, see [here](#). In the `mike/config.yaml` file, we can specify which localizations we want our application to be made available in using the `languages` key, in which case additional language-specific resource files will be generated for those languages as well. (Note that Mike only *creates* these files, but doesn't, at the moment, also *translate* their contents for us.)

When `@title` and `@heading` are used *explicitly* in the descriptor, then the strings specified in their arguments are the ones added to the language resource files. Meanwhile, in cases where a *default title* is displayed even in the *absence* of an explicit `@title` or `@heading`, then *that* default title is added to the language resource files instead! As a consequence, rather than specifying a `@title` at the Mike level, if we prefer, we can also achieve a similar effect by editing the default string in the `messages.properties` file.

Themes and colors

In the aforementioned `mike/config.yaml` file, we can also use the `theme` key to choose from one of three predefined color themes for our application: `LUMO` (the Vaadin default), `MIKE`, or `MYSTIC_SANDS`. We can also opt for a custom theme using `CUSTOM`.

In the latter case, our custom colors can be specified using the `customTheme` key. Under `customTheme / font`, we can specify the `primary` and `base` colors to be used for text, while under `customTheme / scheme`, the specified `base`, `primary`, and `shade` colors will be used for backgrounds.

Here is an example of a `config.yaml` file with a custom theme:

```
mainMikeFile: main.mike
java:
  package:
    base: com.yourpackage.app
projectName: test-project
theme: CUSTOM
customTheme:
  font:
    primary: '#BD1111FF'
    base: '#448769FF'
  scheme:
    primary: '#565C44FF'
    base: '#444444FF'
    shade: '#D5D1B2FF'
```

5. Specialized data modelling features

In this chapter, we return to the `data` section of the descriptor, and review the remainder of Mike's data modelling features.

Built-in types

We have already seen some of the built-in types in action:

- `String` (textual data),

- Int (numeric data),
- Float (numeric data with a decimal point),
- and Date (a calendar date).

The other available types are:

- DateTime (a date together with a time and a time zone),
- Bool (true or false),
- and UUID (a [universally unique identifier](#)).

Enums

As in many programming languages, we can introduce new enumerated types:

```
entity Customer {
    status: CustomerStatus!
    ...
}

enum CustomerStatus {
    LEAD
    ACTIVE
    VIP @display("VIP")
    INACTIVE
    FORMER
}
```

In the CRM context, we can use this to keep track of the current status of our relationships to our customers. To specify the displayed form of the values, we can use `@display`: by default, names are converted to “*Sentence case*” just as with titles, so in this case, the name `VIP` would have resulted in the default textual form “*Vip*”, which is not ideal, since it’s an acronym.

If needed, we can also customize the `enum`’s database storage type and representation:

```
enum CustomerStatus: Int {
    case LEAD @storedAs(100)
    case ACTIVE @storedAs(500)
    case VIP @display("VIP") @storedAs(1000)
    case INACTIVE @storedAs(50)
    case FORMER @storedAs(10)
}
```

The two possible storage types are `Int` and `String`. The default, if not otherwise specified (as we’ve done using `CustomerStatus: Int` above), is `String`.

The `@storedAs` attribute specifies the database representation for an individual `case` (which is the *optional* keyword for `enum` members). If the storage type is `Int`, then by *default*, they would

be stored as *0*, *1*, *2*, and so on, in the same order as listed in the `enum`. The storage type *must* be explicitly specified in order to use `@storedAs`, and if the storage type is `Int`, then (to avoid potential ambiguities) `@storedAs` must be specified for either *all* of the `cases` or for none of them. If the storage type is `String`, then whether to use `@storedAs` can be chosen on a case-by-case basis, and the default representation is simply the name of the `case` in textual form (e.g., "ACTIVE").

Constraints and indexes

Although in our CRM system, customers are primarily identified by their e-mail addresses, we may also wish to enforce that two customers can't have the same phone number. We can do this using a `@unique` attribute:

```
entity Customer {
    email: String @primary
    phoneNumber: String @unique
    ...
}
```

In some cases, we want the *combination* of the values of *multiple* members to be unique across the entire database. For example, if we were to separately record a `Product` entry for each released *version* of a given product, then it would be acceptable for two `Products` to have the same name (as long as their versions differ), or of course the same version (provided they have different names), but if *both* of these were to coincide, that would be a problem. We can represent this constraint using a *composite* `@unique` constraint at the `entity` level:

```
entity Product @unique(name, version) {
    id: UUID @primary
    name: String!
    version: Int!
    ...
}
```

In fact, when `@unique` is specified on a single member such as `phoneNumber` above, this is merely shorthand for `@unique(phoneNumber)` on the `entity`!

(In principle, we might have wanted to go further and actually *identify* products by the combination of their name and version, which would correspond to a `composite @primary` constraint. Unfortunately, these are not yet supported. The above solution using `@unique` is, however, equivalent in most respects.)

When used on a member that refers to an `entity`, `@unique` gives rise to a one-to-one relationship:

```
entity Customer {
    billingInfo: BillingInfo @mappedBy(customer)
```

```

    ...
}

entity BillingInfo {
    id: UUID @primary
    customer: Customer! @unique
    billingAddress: String!
    creditCardLast4: String!
    paymentMethod: PaymentMethod!
}

```

(As before, declaring the `@mappedBy` side of the relationship is optional.)

Observe that since `BillingInfo.customer` is specified as `@unique`, there can be *at most one* `BillingInfo` object that refers to any given `Customer`, and therefore, the type of `Customer.billingInfo` is also simply `BillingInfo` (scalar!), rather than `[BillingInfo]`, as it would have to be in the absence of `@unique`. (For most purposes, which side of the relationship is the `@unique` one, and which the `@mappedBy` one, can be chosen arbitrarily. One notable difference is that only the `@unique` side can be made `@mandatory`, because on the `@mappedBy` side, we can't require *another* entity instance, referring back to this one, to actually exist in the database.)

In a similar manner to how `@unique` constraints are declared, we can also request the creation of database indexes for given members or combinations of members. For example, supposing we needed to store a large number of `Sale` instances and frequently query them by date:

```

entity Sale {
    date: Date @indexed
    ...
}

```

(This attribute is only for optimization purposes, and doesn't affect the behavior of the application in any way beyond its performance characteristics.)

Note that `@unique` and `@primary` already imply the creation of database indexes for those members, so manually specifying `@indexed` as well is unnecessary. And while we omit providing an example here, the composite `@indexed(member1, member2, ...)` attribute on entities can be used in a completely analogous way to the composite `@unique(...)` described earlier, as well.

Default and system-computed values

If an entity member has a sensible default value, we can specify it using the aptly named `@default` attribute:

```

entity Customer {
    status: CustomerStatus! @default(LEAD)
}

```

```

    ...
}

entity Product {
    version: Int! @default(1)
    ...
}

```

These defaults will be reflected as the default values for input fields in create forms, and will be stored to the database if the end user doesn't select a different value. The attribute's argument must be a value of the same type as of the given member. In the case of `enums`, this takes the form of the name of the chosen `case`.

For members which should have their values determined *entirely* by the system, rather than by the end user, we can use the `@value` attribute:

```

entity Customer {
    lastModified: DateTime @value(MODIFIED_AT)
    ...
}

entity Product {
    discontinued: Date @value(DELETED_AT)
    ...
}

entity Sale {
    date: Date @value(CREATED_AT)
    totalAmount: Float @value(COMPUTED)
    ...
}

```

There are currently five supported arguments: `CREATED_AT`, `MODIFIED_AT`, `DELETED_AT`, `IS_DELETED`, and `COMPUTED`.

The first three of these will store the date/time when, logically enough, the entity instance was first created, last modified (including initial creation, if there have been no changes since then), or soft deleted, respectively. (When using hard deletion, of course, there would be no object or record left to store the value in!)

All three of these can be used with members of type `Date` as well as `DateTime`. In the case of `DELETED_AT`, the member will be null *until* it is deleted, while `CREATED_AT` and `MODIFIED_AT` both implicitly activate the `@mandatory` attribute as well. Meanwhile, `@value(IS_DELETED)` is analogous to `DELETED_AT`, except that it can (only) be used on members of type `Bool`, and will result in its value being set from `false` to `true` when soft deletion occurs.

Each of these attributes may be used at most once per `entity`.

The `@value(Computed)` attribute is similar to the others in the sense that the member's value is system-determined, except that in this case, the procedure to do so isn't provided directly by Mike. Instead, this attribute is meant to be used when we've written a procedure to determine the member's value in the application's generated code *ourselves* (in the above example, by summing the `prices` of the sold `products`). The primary effect of this attribute is that the member will *not* be present in the default create and edit forms. (N.B., if we want to use `@value(Computed)` together with `@mandatory`, we *must* also provide a `@default` value for technical reasons, so that the object is possible to construct.)

6. Working with generated code

Merges and conflicts

After Mike generates code for us, we can develop this code further ourselves to better suit our individual requirements. And at the same time, we can *also* continue to modify the Mike descriptor to make high-level changes in the application, and then have Mike re-generate the code for it.

If we modify *both* the descriptor *and* the generated code, the results are then *merged* together. (If you've used a version control system such as `git` before, then you may already be familiar with this process.) Conceptually, it's as if Mike first checks the current state of the generated code to see what changes we've made since the last time Mike generated it for us, then generates a "clean" copy based on the newest version of the descriptor file, and finally, re-applies our custom changes on top of the new version of the generated code.

If the changes made by us and by Mike affect separate parts of the code, then we have nothing further to do! However, if both changes affect the *same* lines, then this results in a *conflict*. (Again, those with prior experience using version control systems may already be familiar with this phenomenon.)

In the event of a conflict, Mike will produce a message reminding us what to do:

```
[CONFLICTS]
  src/main/java/com/yourpackage/app/entity/Test.java
```

Please fix those conflicts and run the following commands: "mike resolve".
In case of conflict you can also undo your changes with the following commands: "mike abort".

Suppose the conflict arose because in the generated code, in the `Test.java` file, we changed the type of the `value` member from `Integer` to `Double`, while, in the Mike descriptor, we changed its *name* from `value` to `distance`. Then, after running `mike generate`, the file will end up containing sections like this one:

```
<<<<<< HEAD
public Double getValue() {
    return value;
}
public void setValue(Double value) {
=====
public Integer getDistance() {
    return distance;
}
public void setDistance(Integer distance) {
>>>>>> 1a58548c875425631e65c8948e14dda433e025cc
```

The `<<<<<<`, `=====`, and `>>>>>>` lines are known as *conflict markers* and divide this section of code into two versions: above, with the changes we made manually, and below, with the changes that Mike made in the generated code as a result of us changing the descriptor. In this particular case, to correctly resolve the conflict, we need to rewrite the code to incorporate *both* changes at the same time, and then remove the conflict markers:

```
public Double getDistance() {
    return distance;
}
public void setDistance(Double distance) {
```

(In other situations, it may also happen that we want to keep one or the other set of changes in their *entirety*, and throw the other one away.)

After we've fixed *all* sections of the code that had conflict markers in the same way, then the last step is to run `mike resolve`, which will finalize the results of the initial `mike generate` command which had detected and reported the conflict.

Alternatively, if, upon seeing the conflict, our reaction is to go “oops” because that wasn't supposed to happen, then we can run `mike abort` to restore the state of the code to what it was before we ran the `mike generate` command. (This affects only the generated code, not the Mike file. In the absence of other changes, if we were to run `mike generate` again, then the same conflict would most likely reoccur.)

Interoperating with pre-existing code

Suppose we have some hand-written Java classes for Hibernate entities, and/or some pre-existing Java `enum` types, and we want to use these together with Mike. That is, we already have, for example, a `Customer` class in Java, and we *don't* want Mike to generate that for us, but we *do* want to *use* the `Customer` type on the Mike side, to display a table of `Customers` in the UI, for example.

This is what the `@external` attribute is for. If we apply this attribute to an entity or an `enum` declaration, then Mike will skip generating the code for it, but will still generate the code for every *other* part of the application *as if* that type's code had also been generated. So, when using

this attribute, we need to take special care that our own `class`'s or `enum`'s definition is compatible with the conventions and APIs used by Mike-generated code!